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PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTI HYPERTENSIVE IR GRANULES AND ANTI DIABETIC SR MINI TABLETS FILLED CAPSULE SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study is to formulate and evaluate the Capsule system with the anti diabetic mini tablets of Glipizide and antihypertensive granules of Losartan potassium with different release patterns by using suitable Excipients. Ethyl cellulose is used as a release retarding polymer in various concentrations in the formulation of the Glipizide mini tablets and the Losartan potassium granules were prepared by using Crospovidone as a super Disintegrant in various concentrations for the immediate drug release. The drug Excipient compatibility studies were performed by FTIR spectroscopy. The pre formulation studies were performed. The in vitro drug release studies were carried out by using the dissolution Apparatus - II at 100rpm in 0.1N HCl for Losartan potassium and 50rpm in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer for Glipizide as described in USP. The simultaneous estimation of both the drugs was carried out by using ultra violet spectroscopy. Optimized formulations are filled in to the hard gelatin capsule systems by using the working formula mentioned above. Formulation CF2 and CF3 showed the best results for the losartan potassium IR (immediate releasing) granules and Glipizide SR (sustained releasing) mini tablets simultaneously. Stability studies were performed for optimized formulation. The capsule systems were observed for accelerated stability studies for a period of two months the obtained results were within specifications.

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, combined therapy with drugs of different therapeutic effects shows an effective way in treatment of diseases and tissue re born. In order to optimize their effects, different drugs should be used at their optimal dose and different periods in the treatment. One of the main challenges of combined therapy is to control the release behaviour of each drug independently.

On the basis of these considerations, we have proposed a new oral delivery device, in the form of anti hypertensive IR granules and anti diabetic SR mini tablets filled capsule systems, in which the one portion is formulated to obtain a prompt release of the drug, with the aim of reaching a high serum concentration in a short period of time. The second portion is a prolonged-release hydrophilic matrix, which is designed to maintain an effective plasma level for a prolonged period of time.

This system can produce a rapid rise in the plasmatic concentrations for some drugs (such as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive and antihistaminic agents) that are requested to promptly exercise the therapeutic effect, followed by an extended release phase in order to avoid repeated administrations. The pharmacokinetic advantage relies on the fact that drug release from fast releasing granules leads to a sudden rise in the blood concentration. However, the blood level is maintained at steady state as the drug is released from the sustaining mini tablets.

Mini tablets (MTs) are small tablets with a diameter typically equal to (or) less than 3mm that are filled into a capsule or occasionally further compressed into larger tablets.

Advantages

- Mini tablets have diameter of 2-3mm can be manufactured with higher Reproducibility compared to pellets,
- Especially regarding their weight and equal Dimensions with smooth regular surface, high strengths and low porosity.
- MTs are less dependent on gastric emptying resulting in less inter-intra subject variation in gastrointestinal transit time.
- These are better distributed and less likely to cause local irritation.
- Fast onset of action due to higher surface area.
- A high degree of dispersion in digestive tract, less absorption variability and a lesser risk of dose dumping.

Granulation is the process in which primary powder particles are made to adhere to form larger, multi particle entities called granules with the size range between 0.2 and 0.5 mm.

Advantages:

- Granules are more easily wetted by solvents.
- Granules are more stable physically and chemically than powders.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Glipizide, Losartan potassium was gifted by Hetero. Ethyl cellulose, Crospovidone, Sodium starch glycolate, Micro crystalline cellulose, Magnesium stearate, Hydrochloric acid, Sodium hydroxide, Methanol were purchased from Finar Chemicals.

Preparation of Losartan potassium IR granules with crospovidone:

For the immediate drug release Losartan potassium granules were prepared with wet granulation method using Crospovidone as a super disintegrant in various concentrations

Table 1 formulation of Losartan IR granules (LC).

S. NO	INGREDIENTS(Mg)/CAPSULE SYSTEM	FORMULATION				
		LC1	LC2	LC3	LC4	LC5
1	LOSARTANPOTASSIUM	50	50	50	50	50
2	CROSPVIDONE	25	50	75	100	125
3	MCC	5	5	5	5	5
TOTAL WEIGHT		80	105	130	155	180

Preparation of Losartan potassium IR granules with sodium starch glycolate

Losartan potassium granules were prepared with wet granulation method using sodium starch glycolate as a super disintegrant in various concentrations for the immediate drug release.

Table 2 formulation of Losartan IR granules (LS).

S NO	INGREDIENTS(Mg)/CAPSULE SYSTEM	FORMULATION				
		LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS5
1	LOSARTAN POTASSIUM	50	50	50	50	50
2	SSG	5	10	15	20	25
3	MCC	5	5	5	5	5
TOTAL WEIGHT		60	65	70	75	80

Preparation of Glipizide SR mini tablets:

The sustained mini tablets of Glipizide are prepared with direct compression method using ethylcellulose in different concentrations as the drug release retarding polymer.

Table 3 formulation of SR mini tablets (G).

S.NO	INGREDIENTS(Mg) /CAPSULE SYSTEM	FORMULATION				
		G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
1	GLIPIZIDE	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
2	ETHYLCELLULOSE	41	42	43	44	45
3	MCC	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
4	MAGNESIUM STEARATE	4	3	2	1	0
TOTAL WEIGHT		50	50	50	50	50

Preparation of IR granules and SR mini tablets filled capsule systems

The prepared mini tablets of Glipizide and Losartan potassium are filled manually in to the Gelatin capsules by following the working formula mentioned below:

Table 4 formulation of IR granuls and SR mini tablets filled capsule systems (CF).

S NO	INGREDIENTS(Mg)	FORMULATION					
		CF1	CF2	CF3	CF4	CF5	CF6
1	GLIPIZIDE	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
2	LOSARTANPOTASSIUM	50	50	50	50	50	50
3	ETHYLCELLULOSE	43	44	45	43	44	45
4	CROSPVIDONE	75	100	125	0	0	0
5	SSG	0	0	0	15	20	25
6	MCC	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5
7	MAGNESIUMSTEARATE	2	1	0	2	1	0
TOTAL WEIGHT		180	205	230	120	125	130

Fig. No. 1: Granules and mini tablets filled capsule systems.

Evaluation of Losartan IR granules:

Bulk density, Tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, Angle of Repose, Dissolution test.

Evaluation of Glipizide SR mini-tablets:

Uniformity of weight, Thickness, Hardness, Dissolution test.

Evaluation of capsule systems:

Disintegration Time, Drug Content, In-vitro Drug Release Study, Stability Study as Per ICH Guideline.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Physical characterization of API'S:**

DESCRIPTION	GLIPIZIDE	LOSARTAN
Colour	White	White
Morphology	Crystalline	Crystalline
Taste	Metallic	Metallic

The solubility studies of API'S:

SOLVENT	GLIPIZIDE	LOSARTAN
Water	Insoluble	Insoluble
0.1N NaOH	Soluble	Soluble
0.1N HCl	Soluble	Soluble
Methanol	Soluble	Soluble
Ethanol	Soluble	Soluble

X RAY DIFFRACTOMETER:

The sharp peaks of the diffractogram in the range of $2\theta = 2$ to 30 indicate the crystallinity of the powder sample.

Fig. No. 2: X ray diffraction of Glipizide.

Fig. No. 3: X ray diffraction of Losartan potassium.

Fig. No. 4: Compatibility studies of Drug and excipients by FTIR.

A – Losartan potassium, B – Losartan + Glipizide, C – Losartan + crospovidone, D – Losartan + Sodium starch glycolate.

Fig. No. 5: Compatibility studies of Drug and excipients by FTIR.

A – Glipizide , B – Gliptide + Losartan , C- Glipizide + Ethyle cellulose.

Table 5 Losartan potassium IR granules evaluation.

Formulation Code	Angle of repose	Carr's Index	Hausner's ratio	% Drug content
LC1	32.14±0.18	26.16±0.23	1.29±0.05	99.15±0.4
LC2	39.21± 0.15	31.12± 0.14	1.41 ±0.07	99.52±0.3
LC3	17.67±0.35	18.27± 0.09	1.25± 0.02	99.98±0.5
LC4	18.41± 0.12	19.35± 0.05	1.22 ±0.02	99.89±0.4
LC5	22.36±0.54	20.32±0.09	1.32±0.63	99.48±0.6
LS1	26.41±0.64	19.54±0.81	1.39±0.51	98.80±0.3
LS2	19.52 ±0.85	18.05± 0.14	1.23± 0.03	99.45±0.4
LS3	21.25 ±0.45	17.46 ±0.25	1.24± 0.05	99.97±0.5
LS4	23.29 ±1.25	19.57 ±0.18	1.25± 0.01	99.78±0.6
LS5	27.29±0.42	21.91±0.72	1.54±0.41	99.25±0.7

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3).

Table 6 Glipizide SR mini tablets evaluation.

Formulation code	Hardness(kg)	Friability (%)	%Drug content	%Weight variation
G1	5.4±0.08	0.34	99.45±0.6	1.05±0.012
G2	5.17±0.06	0.28	99.81±0.4	1.12±0.008
G3	5.63±0.07	0.20	99.89±0.3	1.07±0.009
G4	6.06±0.05	0.29	99.85±0.5	1.24±0.008
G5	5.85±0.05	0.25	99.97±0.4	1.02±0.007

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 7: % Drug release of losartan IR granules with crospovidone.

Time (min)	%Drug release of losartan IR granules with crospovidone				
	LC1	LC2	LC3	LC4	LC5
0	0	0	0	0	0
15	46.79±0.7	51.08±0.3	51.7±0.7	58.42±0.4	53.82±0.4
30	59.46±0.5	62.31±0.5	75.64±0.4	76.47±0.3	73.06±0.7
45	77.9±0.6	81.43±0.3	82.15±0.5	80.44±0.5	81.91±0.6
60	85.89±0.4	87.58±0.5	89.46±0.3	88.79±0.4	86.53±0.3
75	89.62±0.3	91.05±0.7	93.19±0.4	91.65±0.7	90.77±0.4
90	92.14±0.5	93.61±0.6	96.48±0.6	94.03±0.6	93.42±0.5
105	94.58±0.4	95.85±0.5	98.31±0.3	97.91±0.4	96.38±0.4
120	96.86±0.3	97.57±0.4	99.87±0.5	98.9±0.5	97.64±0.5

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Fig. No. 6: % Drug release of Losartan IR granules with crospovidone.

Table 8 %Drug release of losartan IR granules with sodium starch glycolate.

Time (min)	%Drug release of losartan IR granules with sodium starch glycolate				
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS5
0	0	0	0	0	0
15	31.68±0.4	33.65±0.4	34.21±0.6	35.79±0.5	37.19±0.7
30	51.26±0.6	55.09±0.5	55.72±0.4	58.53±0.6	59±0.4
45	74.99±0.7	75.8±0.5	76.31±0.3	77.65±0.4	77.31±0.6
60	81.73±0.3	84.57±0.4	85.53±0.5	80.87±0.5	83.66±0.5
75	88.63±0.5	90.07±0.6	88.96±0.8	86.27±0.3	87.52±0.3
90	90.15±0.6	93.48±0.7	93.47±0.7	92.42±0.4	90.79±0.5
105	91.81±0.5	97.19±0.4	98.28±0.5	97.03±0.5	94.54±0.4
120	92.87±0.3	98.84±0.5	99.75±0.4	98.71±0.3	97.48±0.6

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Fig. No. 7: % Drug release of Losartan IR granules with sodium starch glycolate.

Table 9 %Drug release of Glipizide SR mini tablets.

Time(hrs)	%Drug release of Glipizide SR mini tablets				
	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	9.65±0.4	7.21±0.5	6.58±0.4	5.48±0.6	5.21±0.7
2	14.59±0.6	11.65±0.4	9.73±0.6	9.58±0.5	9.26±0.3
3	51.27±0.3	49.74±0.3	47.21±0.5	44.9±0.7	41.28±0.4
4	59.09±0.5	58.14±0.6	56.93±0.7	52.84±0.5	47.99±0.5
5	68.64±0.4	67.47±0.7	66.09±0.2	62.7±0.4	53.82±0.4
6	72.45±0.3	70.84±0.5	70.81±0.5	69.99±0.5	59.08±0.5
7	78.1±0.7	76.63±0.4	76.42±0.7	73.64±0.3	62.34±0.6
8	81.3±0.6	79.89±0.4	79±0.6	79.9±0.5	71.46±0.3
9	85.77±0.4	82.58±0.5	81.94±0.4	81.24±0.4	74±0.5
10	89.9±0.5	87.95±0.3	87.75±0.5	87.25±0.5	85.76±0.4

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Fig. No. 8: % Drug release of Glipizide SR mini tablets.

Table 10 %Drug release of losartan IR granules with crospovidone and SSG.

Time (min)	%Drug release of losartan IR granules with crospovidone and SSG					
	CF1	CF2	CF3	CF4	CF5	CF6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	51.06±0.7	51.72±0.3	58.42±0.7	33.64±0.4	34.21±0.4	35.8±0.3
30	62.32±0.5	75.82±0.5	76.47±0.4	55.11±0.3	55.74±0.7	58.56±0.5
45	81.41±0.6	82.17±0.3	80.45±0.5	76.32±0.5	76.32±0.6	77.67±0.6
60	87.58±0.4	89.48±0.5	88.76±0.3	85.54±0.4	85.51±0.3	80.88±0.5
75	91.05±0.3	93.19±0.7	91.62±0.4	88.97±0.7	88.92±0.4	86.29±0.7
90	93.62±0.5	96.48±0.6	94.04±0.6	93.48±0.6	93.48±0.5	92.45±0.5
105	95.83±0.4	98.36±0.5	97.92±0.3	97.2±0.4	98.29±0.4	97.05±0.4
120	97.57±0.3	99.87±0.4	98.9±0.5	98.84±0.5	99.75±0.5	98.71±0.6

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Fig. No.9: % Drug release of losartan IR granules with crospovidone and SSG.**Table 11 % Drug release of Glipizide SR mini tablets.**

Time (Hrs)	%Drug release of Glipizide mini tablets					
	CF1	CF2	CF3	CF4	CF5	CF6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	39.41±0.5	37.97±0.4	35.26±0.3	39.4±0.4	37.97±0.6	35.25±0.4
4	59.09±0.3	58.14±0.6	52.84±0.5	59.09±0.3	58.15±0.3	52.85±0.7
6	72.45±0.4	70.84±0.4	70.8±0.7	72.45±0.7	70.85±0.5	70.8±0.4
8	81.3±0.7	79.89±0.5	79.8±0.4	81.3±0.5	79.88±0.4	79.8±0.6
10	89.92±0.5	87.65±0.2	85.76±0.6	89.9±0.3	87.65±0.5	85.76±0.3
12	97.75±0.6	97.24±0.5	97.03±0.3	97.8±0.6	97.25±0.7	97.05±0.5

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Fig. No. 10: % Drug release of Glipizide SR mini tablets.

Table 12 stability studies of the optimized formulation at 40°C and 75%RH for 1 month in a stability chamber.

%Drug release	Time in days		
	1	30	60
Losartan (CF2)	97.24±0.7	97.22±0.4	97.16±0.5
Glipizide (CF3)	97.75±0.5	97.72±0.6	97.68±0.8

All values Expressed as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Fig. No. 11: stability studies of the optimized formulation by FTIR.

CONCLUSION

Losartan potassium and Glipizide are antihypertensive and anti diabetic drugs respectively. The present research was carried out to develop a capsule system with granules of Losartan Potassium by using Crospovidone and Sodium Starch Glycolate as Super disintegrant in various concentrations for immediate release, Where ethyl cellulose is used as the release retarding polymer in various concentrations to Sustain the release of Glipizide

Physical drug and excipients compatibility FT-IR studies revealed there was no interaction between drugs and excipients. Different formulations were prepared in increasing concentrations of super disintegrants and polymers. Wet granulation for immediate release and direct compression was done for Sustained release mini tablets. The prepared batches were evaluated for hardness, friability, drug content uniformity and in-vitro dissolution studies.

Among the ten formulations of losartan potassium granules LC2, LC3, LC4 and LS2, LS3, LS4 are optimized. Among the 5 formulations of Glipizide minitabets G3, G4 and G5 formulation showed best result.

Optimized formulations are filled in to the hard gelatine capsule systems by using the working formula mentioned above. Formulation CF2 and CF3 showed the best results for the losartan potassium IR granules and Glipizide mini tablets simultaneously. Stability studies were performed for optimized formulation. The capsule systems were observed for accelerated stability studies for a period of two months the obtained results were within specifications.

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